

The Unjournal

Evaluation 2 of "Legalizing Entrepreneurship"

Evaluator 2 (anonymous) for The Unjournal

Published on: Jun 11, 2024

URL: <https://unjournal.pubpub.org/pub/legalizingentrepreneurshipe2>

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Review of Multidimensional poverty in the Colombian pacific: identification, measurement and recent trends

Diego Astorga-Rojas¹ 7th April 2024

First Impressions

This paper studies how entrepreneurship in Colombia was affected by a nation wide policy that made almost half a million undocumented migrants from Venezuela eligible for residents visas (PEPProgram). The authors find that having a visa did increased the levels of entrepreneurship among this population.

Strenghts

- It is an amazing paper to read. Very well written, specially since the context of the policy is key for understanding the logic of the methodology used.
- Its contributions are both empirical and methodological. In the empirical part, it studies entrepreneurship, an outcome that has not been studied much in the literature of gains from legalizing migration. The methodological contribution is the application of the new methods that study how to get casual estimates when there is a non random exposure to an exogenous shock. They translate these methods to the context of a regression discontinuity design and propose an instrument for differences between the predicted and actual realizations of running variable. This is one of the most novel parts of the article. • Apart from the proposed methodology and its instrument, it also uses a regular panel method which provides similar results for the main specification.

Suggestions

I find it hard to make comments criticising this paper, however, some ideas have come to mind that might be useful to think about them, either as a robustness check or a possible extension.

1. The article find "similar impacts on the creation of both employer and non-employer firms. While these employer firms create to 6 new jobs and are not "high growth" by the typical standards of developed countries, they still represent meaningful economic spillovers." I wonder if it would be possible to try to study some of these economic spillovers. For example using employer-employee matched data from the "Planilla Integrada de Liquidación de Aportes (PILA)" one could study the effect of obtaining the PEP Pardon on the likelihood of obtaining a job in these new firms created by Venezuelans. If there is an effect, it would be related with the literature of the importance of networks in the job market like for example Calvo-Armengol (2004) or Kramarz and Skans (2014).

2.

- In the panel specification, basically its like a diff in diff approach between those who receive and did not receive PEP. It is not that clear to me why those who did not receive it, see an increase (albeit much lower) in entrepreneurship (see figure 7). Did something change?
3. If there is also the date on where these persons received the visa, one could also use the panel data for an event study instead of a diff in diff, as a robustness check.
 4. The treatment effect by year seems to be statistically significant until 2022 and 2021 (figure 6). I was wondering about the mechanism that might explain this lagged effect. My prior is that to start a business, although having access to the banking and borrowing systems are definitely important, having a credit history in a bank is as important and takes longer. The effects of the event study might be comparable with the findings on figure 6.
 5. This is speculative, but you can use the identification of Bahar, Ib´an˜ez and Rozo (2021) at the municipal level to see aggregate effects in entrepreneurship. If its only the sum of firms of persons with the PEP pardon, it would be a robustness check in the aggregate of some sorts. If it is new firms in general, it would include the direct effect of having more entrepreneurs and the indirect effect of having a larger pool of workers, which might benefit all firms because of a potential cheaper labor. Although, given figure 6, it seems there is no effect for Colombian native firms.
 6. An improvement in the identification of papers like Bahar, Ib´an˜ez and Rozo (2021) might be done also. In there, they use as a instrument the average registration days available by department. One could compute also not only the actual average registration days available by department but also the expected one, using the same permutations done in the paper.

Minor Suggestions

7. In the introduction, in the first page, the authors argue that they in the panel data approach, they can decompose the immigrant entrepreneurship effect into a physical relocation effect and a visa effect. I firstly understood it as if the PEP-Pardon had an effect in migration towards different cities (for example, if I am going to open a business, maybe a big city like Medell´ın or Bogot´a would be better). Then later in the text is explain that the physical reallocation effect is moving from Venezuela to Colombia. It could be my reading but it might be worth it to re check it.
8. Although it is a very good idea to present the assumptions in a general context. It would be useful if at the end of each assumption, you state for the case of the paper what would that mean. It would help the reader to think straightforward is the assumption is getting realized in the case of the study and to think in potential treats in a more direct way.
- 9.

Table 8 and Table 9 show results for different sub-samples. In here, the results in the panel regression differs from the results using the IV cross-section. It would be important to explain this differences.

Conclusions

Overall I find the paper very interesting, both methodologically and empirically. It is very well done and I would think it is very likely to be published in a very good journal. I am not an expert in this field nor in the econometric procedure but I would start by aiming, with a paper like this, for a top general interest journal, and see from there comments and feedback from those type of reviewers.

References

Bahar, Dany, Ana Mar´ıa Ib´an˜ez, and Sandra V Rozo. 2021. "Give me your tired and your poor: Impact of a large-scale amnesty program for undocumented refugees." *Journal of Development Economics*, 151: 102652.

Calv´o-Armengol, Antoni. 2004. "Job contact networks." *Journal of Economic Theory*, 115(1): 191– 206.

Kramarz, Francis, and Oskar Nordstr´om Skans. 2014. "When strong ties are strong: Networks and youth labour market entry." *Review of Economic Studies*, 81(3): 1164–1200.

Footnotes

1. Departamento de Econom´ıa, Pontificia Universidad Javeriana, E-mail: astorgarl@javeriana.edu.co ↵